

Synergistic Extraction and Simultaneous Determination of Nickel and Copper

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o-Mercapto acetoacetanilide can be used for the quantitative determination of nickel and copper in presence of γ -picoline as a synergistic agent. The complexes are extractable in the pH ranges 5.0-7.0 and 6.0-7.6 in chloroform layer and the λ_{\max} values are 615 and 630 nm for the two metals, respectively. The molar absorptivities of these complexes are $5.21 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for nickel and $5.57 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for copper. Sandell sensitivities for the metals are 0.05 and 0.01 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. Beer's law is obeyed over the ranges 0.5-120.0 ppm with r.s.d. $\pm 0.92\%$ for nickel and 0.1-9.0 ppm with r.s.d. $\pm 0.68\%$ for copper. Tolerance limits and the interferences of different foreign ions have been studied. Nickel and copper can be determined simultaneously in ores and alloys. The nature of the two complexes has been discussed.

THE extraction of divalent metal ions of the first transition series with β -diketone and pyridine base synergic agent has been reported by many authors¹⁻¹³. The extraction of the nickel(II)- β -diketonate is practically difficult without the aid of synergism. The reagents used for the spectrophotometric determination of copper are innumerable. The ligands with 1:3-diketo group e.g., 1,1,1-trifluoro-3-(2-thenoyl)-acetone¹⁴ and acetoacetanilide¹⁵ have been successfully used as reagents for copper(II). The extraction of such complexes is likely to be enhanced, if synergistic extractions are carried out. The work in this field, however, is scanty¹⁶. In the present investigation, the synergistic effect of γ -picoline in the determination of nickel(II) and copper(II) with *o*-mercapto acetoacetanilide ($\text{HSC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOCH}_2\text{COCH}_3$, *o*-MAA) has been studied.

Experimental

Apparatus: Absorbance was measured in a Beckman double beam (Model 26) UV-visible spectrophotometer using a pair of matched 1 cm quartz cuvettes. The pH values were read with a Beckman Zeromatic pH-meter. The ir spectrum was recorded on a Beckman ir spectrophotometer (Acculab 10).

***o*-Mercapto acetoacetanilide:** A method of preparation of this new reagent by condensation of *o*-aminothiophenol and ethyl acetoacetate, has been described¹⁷. The yellowish orange compound was recrystallised from rectified spirit. A fresh stock solution of the reagent ($1.25 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) was made in 60% aqueous ethanol.

Nickel(II) solution: A stock solution (0.1 M) of ammonium nickel sulphate (G. R., E. Merck) was prepared in double distilled water. The concentra-

tion was checked gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime¹⁸.

Copper(II) solution: A stock solution ($1.05 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) of copper was prepared by dissolving copper sulphate pentahydrate (A. R., B. D. H.) in double distilled water with a little sulphuric acid. The copper content was determined by titration with EDTA solution¹⁹.

γ -Picoline solution: A 0.1 M aqueous solution of γ -picoline (Fluka) was used.

All other solutions were prepared from A. R. or G. R. grade chemicals.

Procedure for nickel: A 2 ml aliquot of nickel(II) solution containing 150-200 μg of the metal was mixed with 2 ml γ -picoline solution and 2 ml of $1.25 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ reagent solution. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.0 and then 5 ml acetate buffer solution was added. The whole mixture was taken into a separatory funnel and two extractions were performed using 5 ml portions of chloroform. The organic layer was transferred into a calibrated 10 ml volumetric flask after dehydrating with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The absorbance was measured at 615 nm against solvent blank.

Procedure for copper: To a 2 ml aliquot containing 10-100 μg of copper(II) were added 2 ml of γ -picoline solution and 5 ml of $1.25 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ reagent solution. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.5 and then 2 ml acetate buffer solution was added. The rest of the procedure was the same as that for nickel. The absorbance was measured at 630 nm instead of 615 nm.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum: The absorbance values of several extracts containing different amounts of

nickel were measured against solvent blank in the wavelength range of 550-700 nm which showed maximum absorption of 615 nm. Similarly, the maximum was at 630 nm for copper. The reagent curve showed a peak at 390 nm and almost no absorbance above 515 nm. The molar absorptivities for the two complexes at their λ_{max} were respectively 5.21×10^4 and 5.57×10^4 l.mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Calibration and sensitivity: Beer's law was found to be valid over the ranges 0.5-120.0 ppm nickel and 0.1-9.0 ppm copper. According to Sandell²⁰ the optimum concentration ranges were 25.0-80.0 ppm and 2.5-8.0 ppm for nickel and copper, respectively. The corresponding Sandell sensitivities²⁰ were 0.05 μ g nickel cm⁻² and 0.01 μ g copper cm⁻². The relative standard deviations were found to be $\pm 0.92\%$ and $\pm 0.68\%$, respectively. The confidence limits (95%) for 7 determinations were found to be 58.80 ± 0.01 ppm for nickel and 6.73 ± 0.01 ppm for copper.

Effect of pH: The effect of the variation of pH was studied for the efficient extraction of the complexes. The results indicated that pH 5.0-7.0 was suitable for nickel and pH 6.0-7.6 was suitable for copper to produce maximum colour intensity. The presence of magnesium-EDTA was necessary in either case to prevent the formation of any hydroxide due to local concentration of alkali during adjustment of higher pH values.

Effect of reagent concentration: 4.50 mg of the reagent was necessary for complete extraction of 587.0 μ g of nickel(II). Similarly, 0.50 mg of the reagent was necessary for complete extraction of 66.73 μ g of copper(II). However, higher amounts of the reagent did not affect the estimation in either case.

Effect of γ -picoline: Addition of different amounts of γ -picoline to the same amounts of metal-ligand complexes, showed that synergism was attained. Thus, for maximum synergistic effect, 4.0-6.0 ml of 0.1 M γ -picoline solution was required for complete extraction of nickel in the whole working range. Similarly, 1.5-3.0 ml was required for copper estimation.

Extraction efficiency and stability: Chloroform was found to be the most suitable extractant for nickel and copper complexes. The two complexes were recovered to the extent of about 90% and 97%, respectively. The extract for nickel complexes was stable for more than one month whereas that of copper complex was stable for 10 days.

Effect of diverse ions: For the study of the tolerance limits (within relative error $\pm 2\%$) for diverse ions, 587 μ g nickel(II) and 67 μ g copper(II) were taken separately with varying concentrations of other ions and the analysis was carried out by the recommended procedure. A large number of ions caused no interference with the method (Table 1). Estimations were not possible in presence of silver(I), mercury(II), tin(II), gold(III) and cyanide in either case.

TABLE 1—TOLERANCE LIMIT OF VARIOUS IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF Ni(II) AND Cu(II). Metals per ml CHCl₃: 58.7 μ g Ni/6.7 μ g Cu

Estimating metal	Tolerance limit	Diverse ions
Ni(II)	50 mg	Be(II), Ba(II), Ca(II), Mg(II), Sr(II), Zn(II).
	40 mg	Cd(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Ga(III), In(III), Te(IV).
	20 mg	Pb(II), Th(IV), V(IV), Zr(IV), W(VI).
	15 mg	Co(II) ^a , As(III).
	10 mg	Mo(II), Sb(III), Bi(III), Fe(III) ^b .
	2 mg	Pd(II), Pt(II), Ir(III), Rh(III), U(VI), Os(VIII).
	600 mg	F ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ .
	500 mg	Br ⁻ , tartrate.
	250 mg	PO ₄ ³⁻ , Mg-EDTA.
	10 mg	Be(II), Ba(II), Cd(II), Ca(II), Mg(II), Sr(II), Zn(II).
Cu(II)	5 mg	Al(III), Cr(III), Ga(III), In(III), Te(IV), Th(IV), V(IV), Zr(IV), W(VI).
	2 mg	Co(II) ^a , Pb(II), Fe(III) ^b .
	1 mg	Mo(II), Sb(III), As(III), Bi(III).
	0.5 mg	Pd(II), Pt(II), Ir(III), Rh(III), U(VI), Os(VIII).
	120 mg	F ⁻ , Br ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , tartrate.
	80 mg	PO ₄ ³⁻ , Mg-EDTA.

a—in presence of Mg-EDTA, b—in presence of tartrate.

Simultaneous determination of nickel and copper: Several mixtures, containing various quantities of nickel and copper, were taken in separating funnel. 5 ml of 0.1 M γ -picoline and 5 ml of 1.25×10^{-2} M reagent solution were added to it. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.0 and then 5 ml acetate buffer added. Finally, two extractions were performed using 5 ml portions of chloroform. After dehydrating the chloroform layer with anhydrous sodium sulphate, the absorbances were measured at 615 nm and 630 nm. As the individual peaks overlap considerably (Fig. 1) the absorbances of these complexes are additive at both 615 and 630 nm. Thus it

Fig. 1. Overlapping of absorbance curves for nickel(II) and copper(II).

- A 40.0 ppm Ni(II)
- B 3.90 ppm Cu(II)
- R Reagent blank

can be used for simultaneous determination of the two metals, the amounts being found by solving the necessary equations²¹. Typical results for synthetic mixtures are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF NICKEL AND COPPER

Taken μg		Found* μg		Error %	
Ni	Cu	Ni	Cu	Ni	Cu
587.00	67.00	593.80	66.20	+1.1	-1.2
587.00	33.50	583.10	33.40	-0.7	-0.3
293.50	67.00	289.50	67.34	+1.4	+0.5
293.50	33.50	291.60	33.63	-0.6	+0.4

* Average of 3 determinations.

Analyses of the metals in different samples : Several certified samples were analysed after decomposing by the standard methods e.g. steel²² for nickel estimation, white metal²³ and chalcopyrite²⁴ for copper estimation, monel metal²⁵ for both nickel and copper estimation. The results of these determinations by the proposed method have been presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL AND COPPER IN STANDARD SAMPLES

Sample (Certified value)	Found* %		Error %	
	Ni	Cu	Ni	Cu
Steel (Ni=9.48%)	9.41	—	-0.74	—
White metal (Cu=3.0%)	—	2.94	—	-2.0
Chalcopyrite (Cu=31.61%)	—	31.72	—	+0.85
Monel metal (Ni=35.50%) (Cu=68.80%)	35.82	63.16	+0.90	-1.00

* Average of 3 determinations.

Nature of the complexes : Both the complexes were precipitated as green compounds. The results of elemental analysis of the complexes, $M(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{NS})_2(\gamma\text{-picoline})_2$, ($M=\text{Ni}^{2+}$ or Cu^{2+}) were as follows. For the nickel compound, Found : N, 8.41 ; S, 9.71 ; Ni, 8.97. Calcd. ; N, 8.47 ; S, 9.68 ; Ni, 8.88% ; for the copper compound, Found : N, 8.52 ; S, 9.50 ; Cu, 9.61. Calcd. ; N, 8.41 ; S, 9.61 ; Cu, 9.54%. These values were in agreement with metal : ligand : $\gamma\text{-picoline}=1 : 2 : 2$. TGA studies showing a two step decomposition supports this composition. A loss in weight corresponding to 28.18% (corresponds to the loss of 2 molecules of $\gamma\text{-picoline}$) at 511 and 400°, respectively resulted in the formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{o-MAA})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{o-MAA})_2$. The Ni(II)- and Cu(II)- o-MAA complexes were stable upto 700 and 605°, respectively before they showed loss in weights e.g. 88.70% and 87.92% of the original complexes corresponding to the formation of their oxides, NiO and CuO.

The infrared spectra of the complexes were studied in the solid phase using KBr matrix and was compared with that of the ligand²⁴. The following prominent peaks were found. For nickel complex : 3280 cm^{-1} (νNH stretching), 1610 cm^{-1} (νCO), 2380 cm^{-1} (νSH), 1500 cm^{-1} ($\nu\ \gamma\text{-picoline}$) and for copper complex : 3310 cm^{-1} (νNH stretching), 1605 cm^{-1} (νCO), 2380 cm^{-1} (νSH), 1540 cm^{-1} ($\nu\ \gamma\text{-picoline}$). The band at 2380 cm^{-1} in both the cases showed the presence of free SH group as was found in the ligand¹⁷. That the sulphur end of the ligand remains uncoordinated to metal is also found in some other sulphur containing ligands²⁵.

Examination of the electronic spectra of the metal complexes in chloroform showed the intense bands at 16,300 cm^{-1} for nickel and 15,900 cm^{-1} for copper and were assigned for ${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})\rightarrow{}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3\text{E}_g\rightarrow{}^3\text{T}_{2g}$, respectively²⁶. The magnetic moment values for the complexes were 3.10 B.M. and 1.95 B.M., respectively indicating their octahedral structures.

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